

Technical Report: Object Disorientation

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Abstract. This technical report complements our essay “Object Disorientation” with methodological details of the literature search and an in-depth analysis of the how’s and why’s of object orientation. We recommend reading the essay first.

Despite its longstanding history, object-oriented programming (OOP) remains a cornerstone of modern software development. While everyone seems to have an idea of what OOP means, it is surprisingly challenging to operationalize key concepts of OOP due to its widespread but varied perceptions. This makes it difficult for researchers to investigate the paradigm, difficult for practitioners to select suitable technologies, and complicates students’ transfer of OOP knowledge across programming languages. Our study aimed to uncover the essence of OOP—its fundamental ideas, concepts, and principles—through a scoping review of prominent views in scientific and gray literature. In the end, we synthesized two conceptual lines within OOP: understanding “why” and “how” the paradigm is used. Our synthesis reveals they are complementary yet often misunderstood as separate perspectives.

1 Overview

This technical report extends our essay “Object Disorientation” with details on the methodology in Section 2, which includes in particular a network graph of articles included in the scoping review, as well as a discussion of the limitations of our approach. Section 3 goes into the details of what we have only summarized in the essay: the different perspectives on what object orientation means.

2 Notes on Methodology

To address our research question, we conducted a *scoping* review to create a baseline set of understanding of object orientation. Such scoping review is a form of systematic literature review “to understand the status of research on a particular topic, typically by mapping primary studies into categories” [21]. However, it sets limits to the types of literature databases, constraining the date range under investigation, or eliding consistency measures, such as inter-rater agreement [19].

Our search strategy was a *pure snowballing approach*, motivated by evidence that snowballing is similarly effective as and usually more efficient than database searches [4, 13, 35]. As the starting point for our scoping review, we selected Aldrich’s Onward! 2013 essay “The Power of Interoperability: Why Objects Are Inevitable” [3]. We started with this essay because we kept coming back to this article in discussions about object orientation with members of our groups and beyond. Furthermore, this article is often mentioned in blogs about object orientation.⁴ This essay led to some highly cited papers and eventually to the 24 publications that we included in our scoping review. At this point, we have reached information saturation in consideration of our research question.

In Figure 1, we present an overview of 24 articles included in our scoping review. They can be roughly divided into two sets: One set discusses object-orientated features, that is, how it is applied (blue rectangles in Fig. 1). The second set describes *why* object orientation is applied (orange ovals in Fig. 1). In the next section, we discuss both lines of research in detail. White nodes denote articles that could not be unambiguously assigned to one of the views, but since they provide background information and relevant ideas, we kept them for reference (uncolored rectangles with an angled corner in Fig. 1).

Limitations and Further Considerations

We are aware that our search strategy involves selection bias due to the selection of a single article in the start set. However, since we have evaluated in a parallel attempt what results we would achieve with a classic keyword search, we can confidently claim that the overall picture of a diverse understanding of object-oriented programming would still have emerged.

Then, we carefully selected the papers for our scoping review by making sure to include key players in the area of OOP. However, many papers from non-scientific contexts, often written by practitioners, frequently lacked proper source citations. This omission is problematic, as it can lead to unverified information and hinder the reader’s ability to trace ideas back to their origins. Yet, in their defense, these papers often did not claim to be scientifically rigorous, which partly explains the absence of source citations. We further believe that our selection represents a considerable part of the object-oriented community and that the most important aspects are covered. We found that object-oriented programming is inherently disorienting due to a diversity of concepts, opinions and ideas within an object-oriented cloud. Including more papers could further contribute to this diversity, rather than reducing the complexity of the issue, but we are certain that we had reached information saturation at the point at which we stopped including more papers.

⁴ Just to mention a few:

<https://blog.acolyer.org/2014/11/11/the-power-of-interoperability-why-objects-are-inevitable/>
[http://lambda-the-ultimate.org/node/4790/](http://lambda-the-ultimate.org/node/4790)
<https://www.bcobb.net/hacker-school-read-along-the-power-of-interoperability/>

Fig. 1. Network graph of articles included in the scoping review. Numbers in brackets show the citation count registered by Google Scholar at the time of study conduct

3 An In-Depth Analysis of the How’s and Why’s

For interested readers who are keen to delve into the depths of object orientation with us, this section contains detailed elaborations on how and why object orientation is used. This extension of our essay presents the results of our scoping review in greater depth. For an introductory overview of the results, we recommend reading our essay in advance.

3.1 The Formalistic View: How Is Object Orientation Used?

In this section, we discuss several aspects that comprise *how* object orientation is implemented: objects, state & encapsulation, classes, inheritance & composition, messaging, and polymorphism.

Objects *Object-oriented* is a term specific to the programming world. However, it encompasses the term *object*, which is used in everyday language to mean a thing, being, or concept. In the context of programming, the idea of objects appeared simultaneously in different fields in the early 1970s. Objects were considered *units* that allowed programmers to manage the increasing complexity of computer systems [5]. In this context, Simula 67 inhabits a special role. This programming language was created by Dahl and Nygaard and is particularly important because it was probably the first language to uphold the idea of

objects. Dahl and colleagues suggested several syntactic features (e.g., the dot-notation and the keyword `new`), which can still be found in modern programming languages [8]. Many authors consider Simula to be the first object-oriented programming language because it was the first to suggest *classes* to describe recurring patterns of semantic units.

Dahl and others [8] state that “an object is a self-contained program (block-instance), having its own local data and actions defined by a ‘class declaration’” (here, a “block” refers to a code structure in Simula). Placing data and operations closely together was a novel approach at the time. When Simula was conceived, the predominant programming paradigms encouraged defining data structures and procedures separately, where the data was modified and kept separate from the data structures involved. This definition can be understood as the source of the modern understanding of objects. Most authors shared a similar interpretation of this definition: Thomas describes that “an object-oriented programming system (OOPS) doesn’t view an object just as passive data but as the combination of its private state and the methods that manipulate it” [30][pp. 232]. To Wegner [31], “an object has a set of ‘operations’ and a ‘state’ that remembers the effect of operations”.

Although these definitions are roughly equivalent (i.e., an object has something to do with data and operations), they each focus on slightly different aspects of the original definition. The authors define objects by their structural properties: An object is a combination of state and operations. The hermeneutic view, however, adds another conceptual level: Stefik and Bobrow state that objects “being things” that perform computations [28]. Thomas underscores the idea that objects are seen as “active” units, rather than passive data structures [30], and Wegner reduces objects to sets of operations [31].

Here, West’s view on the differences between the hermeneutic and formalist views becomes relevant: The hermeneutic view sees objects as active units of conception (their purpose), while the formalist view looks at the rules that can be enforced upon them [34].

Uniformity Altogether, the authors’ commitment to objects themselves varies. Some see objects as mandatory, others regard them as complementary. Smalltalk embodies the former view. In Smalltalk, any meaningful processing happens in an object and all entities are objects (e.g., even integers). This idea is often abridged to “Everything is an Object” [34]. In this view, objects share the same means to communicate with other objects. Rentsch calls this feature the objects’ *uniformity* [22]. Objects are uniform in that “all elements are equally object-like”, that is, there are no entities with a special status (e.g., integers are also objects). In the Smalltalk view, objects are the central unit to express a program’s function.

Some authors interpret the presence of objects less strictly and accept other mechanisms of computation. For example, Bjarne Stroustrup’s C++ introduced objects to the C programming language, but retained functions and primitive data types (e.g., integers, floats, pointers) as first class citizens of the language [29]. In C++, these entities are not treated uniformly, as objects are complementary resources to express programs, not mandatory ones. Even newer

languages such as Java trade uniformity for performance (e.g., by supporting primitive data types).

In a nutshell, some authors see objects as the unique fundamental building blocks of software [15,22,25,34], whereas other authors are more permissive and underscore that objects can coexist with other building blocks [3,27,29].

Whether or not objects are to be seen as central to computation, they are in the most reduced view understood as a combination of data and operations on these data.

State & Encapsulation The data that objects hold are said to be their *state*. State allows objects to remember the effect of their operations. Wegner explains that state is an essential feature of objects. It can be viewed as memory for an operation’s effect [31] (e.g., storing a computed value). An object that changes its internal state is said to be *mutable*. Such mutable state can affect the outcome of the future invocation of operations. This distinguishes objects from pure functions, which do not remember their previous effects and are considered stateless.

While an object’s capability to hold state appears to be a special feature that distinguishes objects from functions, it is still possible to implement objects without state, or to conceptually simulate the state change of an immutable object by cloning. For example, updating the name of a person object could either result in a change to the object’s internal data, or yield a copy of the object holding the updated value. The object is then considered *immutable* [7]. Thus, some authors conclude that state is not essential to define objects [6,7,27], while others disagree [5,31,33] and define objects as entities having state.

The idea of combining data and operations on these entities is not even unique to the object-oriented paradigm. Reynolds describes a concept he calls *procedural data structures*. Procedural (or “functional”) data structures are collections of operations. The only means to manipulate data is through these operations, as opposed to manipulating the data directly. Procedural data structures separate permitted operations from the structure of the manipulated data. As long as the procedural interaction (i.e., a procedural data structure’s specific procedural interface) remains untouched, the internal details of the manipulated data can be altered (e.g., a stack can be implemented with a linked list or an array), thus providing a “decentralized form of data abstraction” [23]. Reynolds calls this *representational independence*. The mechanism to achieve independence between an internal data structure and an external interface is called *encapsulation*. Liskov describes this mechanism in detail [17]:

To allow changing implementations without affecting users, we need a way of changing the representation without having to change all using programs. This is achieved by encapsulating the rep[resentation] with a set of operations that manipulate it and by restricting using programs so that they cannot manipulate the rep[resentation] directly, but instead must call the operations. [17][pp. 19; bracket terms added by us]

Encapsulation describes the idea that an object should be responsible for its state, and manipulation of an object’s state from outside should be prevented.

Objects *encapsulate* details of the internal data. This allows programmers to substitute these data and change their details, as long as the abstract outside view stays intact [17].

As with the idea of state itself, some authors see encapsulation as essential for objects [16,22,30], while others are more permissive in this regard [7,28,31].

Classes When objects were introduced with Simula, Dahl and others suggested using *classes* to define objects. Today, several interpretations of classes exist, as West points out [34][p. 130]:

1. **Classes as sets:** Classes are groupings or sets of similar objects. This view is upheld by Booch and others [5], who define a class as “[...] a set of objects that share a common structure, common behavior, and common semantics. A single object is an instance of a class”.
2. **Classes as examples:** Classes are declarations that describe exemplar objects (e.g., an object of a class **Person** will have a given name, a surname, etc.). Wegner states [31]: “A class is a template (cookie cutter) from which objects may be created by ‘create’ or ‘new’ operations”.
3. **Classes as storage:** In this view, classes represent a storage location, in that they provide locality for resources, such as data and operations, a view advocated by Liskov [17].
4. **Classes as factories:** Factories are entities whose role is the creation of object instances. Cook defines [6]: “A class is a procedure that returns a value satisfying an interface”, which adheres to this view.

While these definitions are similar to each other, they each apply slightly different semantics: Wegner and Cook see classes as active procedures that create objects, whereas Dahl and colleagues state that objects, when grouped by the same patterns, may “belong to the same class”.

In addition to these different interpretations, authors have different opinions on the relevance of classes: Dahl and colleagues were the first to introduce classes as a mechanism to categorize objects. All authors describe them as a means to group similar behavioral interfaces. However, Wegner describes classes as a primary means to create objects, and regards them as essential to characterize *object-oriented* programming. In his terms, languages that support objects, but not classes or inheritance, are a different category called *object-based* languages. While Dahl and colleagues and Cook mention classes, Wegner underscores their role to define the object-oriented paradigm. Kay underscores that classes are not the central idea of Smalltalk [15], although Smalltalk uses classes extensively.

In a nutshell, different interpretations of the concept of a class exist, and some see classes as fundamental to defining object-oriented programming, whereas others do not. This phenomenon applies to classes themselves, and additionally to all ideas on how classes should be organized in relation to each other. Object-oriented programs usually comprise multiple classes that can be arranged in relationship structures, such as *inheritance* and *composition*, which we discuss next.

Inheritance & Composition A program may consist of many objects, and in such case the objects are often placed in relation to each other. There are different mechanisms to do so, most importantly *inheritance* and *composition*. We discuss inheritance first and then contrast it with composition.

Inheritance In Simula 67, classes can be *prefixed* with other classes (i.e., a class name can be placed in front of another class name). This allows classes to share code of existing classes. Prefixing arranges class definitions into a hierarchical structure, in which a *subclass inherits* operations from a *superclass*, that is, a subclass can access the properties and operations of its superclass. In modern programming languages, this mechanism is called *inheritance*. Using inheritance, classes can share resources within a hierarchy.

Booch and others define inheritance as follows [5]:

Simply stated, inheritance is a relationship among classes, wherein one class shares the structure and/or behavior defined in one or more other classes.
[5][pp. 110]

An alternative approach to this sharing mechanism is *delegation*. An object can delegate the responsibility to perform an operation to another object, while pretending to perform the operation itself. This can be achieved through dynamically binding the responsible object during its execution, making it look as if an operation belongs to multiple different instances.

Inheritance and delegation are related in that they are both mechanisms to share the features of existing entities. Inheritance allows programmers to use existing features of classes, whereas delegation allows objects to use other existing objects. Both concepts can be found in modern programming languages: For example, *inheritance* is part of Java or C#, and *delegation* can be found in JavaScript. JavaScript does not use classes and instead links objects' prototypes in a chain, which is resolved at runtime to identify the object that is responsible to perform an operation.

Inheritance forms a tense relationship with encapsulation. While encapsulation enforces boundaries between objects, inheritance softens these boundaries: Encapsulation shields the internal data representations by allowing an object's clients (i.e., the surrounding environment using the object) to alter these data only through public methods that belong to the object. This allows programmers in control of the object to change the object's internal representation independently from their public presentation through a set of operations.

In contrast, inheritance introduces coupling between classes, in that a subclass can inherit from a superclass to share its implementation details. The subclass has access to many internal details and is free to manipulate them at will. This may prevent changes to be made to an implementation when a subclass depends on the details of a superclass, and so either class cannot be changed independently without changing the other [26].

In a nutshell, encapsulation enforces boundaries between objects and allows to change internal representations independently from its public interface, but inheritance partially antagonizes this mechanism.

Composition Inheritance is a way of sharing functions and data among similar objects. Composition is an alternative mechanism to share functionality by combining objects with each other into new (higher-order) objects. Objects that are assembled this way are called *compositions* or *composite objects* [28]. *Composability* describes the capability of objects to allow such assembly.

To illustrate the idea of composition, imagine a windowing system, which can collect buttons, labels, and border elements to form specific window instances. The window then contains individual objects and allows programmers to interact with them as a unit. This relationship is sometimes called a “part-of-relationship” [30], and is similar to modern machines: A car has an engine, a body, wheels, and seats. They are individual components of the car, but the car can be treated as a whole and thus can be viewed as a composition.

Booch and others outline how elements of complex systems can form either “is-a” or “part-of” hierarchies [5]. For example, a turbofan engine *is a* specific kind of engine, but the engine is *part of* an aircraft. These ideas are analogous to the ideas of inheritance hierarchies, in which classes lower in the hierarchy are refined and more specific versions of classes higher up in the hierarchy (is-a relationships). In contrast, compositions are objects that are combinations of other objects (part-of relationships).

Booch and colleagues offer a finer view of composition. They distinguish *composition* from *aggregation*. Both aggregation and composition are “a whole/part relationship where one object is composed of one or more other objects, each of which is considered a part of the whole”. However, they see aggregation as a “weak form of containment in that the lifetimes of the whole and its parts are independent”. In contrast, composition is a “strong form of aggregation” in that the lifetimes of the parts and the whole are dependent.

While some authors speak of composition as a process, some authors focus on the results. Stefik and Bobrow discuss *composite objects* [28]:

A composite object is a group of interconnected objects that are instantiated together, a recursive extension of the notion of object. A composite is defined by a template that describes the subobjects and their connections.
[28][pp. 51]

Here, the authors describe that composites should be created together. This is equivalent to the conception of a *composition* in the sense of Booch and colleagues by including considerations of object lifetimes. However, central to their conception of composite objects is the idea that objects can be combined to form new objects. That is, they can be *composed*, thus forming composite objects.

Stefik and Bobrow’s conception is similar to West’s idea of *components* [34]. According to West, “a component is a large-grain object made up of several basic objects”. However, Booch and others differentiate components from compositions. To them, a component is:

A logical collection of classes that collaborate to provide a set of services offered through the component’s provided interfaces. [...] A component

may also consist of other components and may be nested to whatever level required. [5][pp. 523]

This definition is similar to the views of Stefik and Bobrow, and West, in that objects can be combined and nested with other objects to create larger structures. When multiple objects are combined to fulfill a higher goal (i.e., to provide service or fulfill tasks rather), they can serve as components, this way supporting reuse.

Composition vs. Inheritance. Both composition and inheritance are means to reuse existing functionality. The mechanism to this end differs: Composition happens during a program's *runtime*, whereas inheritance happens during *design time* (i.e., when classes are defined).⁵ Gamma and others make this difference explicit by calling the relationship *class inheritance* and *object composition* [9].

Composition and inheritance both attempt to facilitate sharing of data and reusing existing implementations. However, Gamma and colleagues recommend preferring object composition over class inheritance. They argue that class hierarchies tie classes together in that changes in a superclass often require changes to be made in a subclass, thus negating the benefit of reuse by requiring additional effort for alterations. Reuse should instead focus on the capability to *compose* objects.

On the one hand, inheritance can be supported by programming languages through type systems and be statically enforced at design time, but it also requires knowledge of the internals of classes when relationships are formed. On the other hand, composition becomes relevant at runtime. Objects are treated as black boxes, and no knowledge of their internals are needed and all interaction happens through their interfaces (i.e., the set of operations the object comprises).

In a nutshell, different authors put different emphasis on the idea of composability. Thomas treats composability as an alternative to inheritance [30]. Gamma and colleagues (1995) underscore the problems caused by inheritance and point out how composition can solve these problems. Stefik and Bobrow discuss composability in isolation and focus on its mechanisms [28]. Booch and colleagues discuss different levels of composability, whereas other authors mean to simply say “putting things together”.

Messaging Various authors mention *messaging*, or a variation of the term (i.e., message sending, message passing) as a means to issue requests to an object with the goal to invoke an operation [16, 30, 31]. The origin of the concept of messaging is commonly attributed to Alan Kay, as it is the primary means to invoke operations in Smalltalk, which Kay developed together with Ingalls [12] and Goldberg and Robson [10]. Kay sees messaging as a primary mechanism of the object-oriented paradigm:

⁵ While some dynamic languages also support the manipulation of inheritance relationships at runtime, this is not common practice and a discouraged design choice.

OOP to me means only messaging, local retention and protection and hiding of state-process, and extreme late-binding of all things. [16]

In this definition, we can find an object-oriented feature that we discussed earlier: “Local retention and protection and hiding of state-process” can be understood as a synonym for *encapsulation*, and, according to Kay, plays a significant role in the object-oriented paradigm. However, the outstanding idea in this definition is Kay’s emphasis on *messaging*.

The messaging metaphor is helpful to convey that objects can implement their own specific versions of operations. An object receives a message and is responsible for performing an action (e.g., performing a calculation). Different objects that receive the same message can perform different actions. For example, a circle object and a rectangle object can both react to a **draw** message, but the performed operations result in different effects (i.e., a circle being drawn or a rectangle, respectively).

Messaging is mentioned by other authors, for example, by Stefik and Bobrow, who see message sending as essential for object-oriented programming [28]. Thomas describes messaging as an important feature in object-oriented programming, and sees it as beneficial, because it allows programmers to easily add objects to an existing system [30]. For example, adding a new triangle shape that responds to a **draw** message does not interfere with existing objects, such as rectangles or circles. Messages are (dynamically) dispatched based on the type of the receiver object.

Different authors focus on slightly different semantics when discussing the notion of messaging. Some authors speak of *messaging*, others of *message passing*, and still others of *message sending*. Thus, there is no agreement which terms to use and whether or not they denote the same concepts. A possible reason for this phenomenon is given by Thomas [30]: Messaging appears to have occurred with the development of Smalltalk (hence Kay’s insistence on the concept), and the confusion regarding messaging can be explained by looking at Smalltalk’s history. Thomas outlines several circumstances:

1. Smalltalk was developed at Xerox Palo Alto Research Center (Xerox PARC) and kept relatively inaccessible to the software community until the release of Smalltalk 80 in 1981.
2. Smalltalk was conceived as a complete programming environment and not just a compiler. For example, it included a virtual-machine runtime and brought its own interactive windowing system. Thus, it is likely that potential users mistook it for a windowing system and were distracted from its novel concepts (e.g., messaging).
3. The Smalltalk environment was implemented to be flexible and changeable, which was implemented using a virtual machine environment and thus required powerful hardware, which limited its spread on the market.

Messaging appeared as one of many ideas specific to Smalltalk. However, Smalltalk had little exposition to the public, because it was not made widely

available. The importance that authors grant to the concept varies between their definitions. Authors who learned about object-oriented concepts through Smalltalk underscore the importance of messaging to define object-oriented programming (e.g., [22, 30]), whereas in the work of others it plays a minor role.

Wegner mentions messaging in the scope of actor languages (e.g., IO, Act1, Erlang). Actor languages are related, but not equivalent to, object-oriented languages. While object-oriented languages have objects, classes, and inheritance, actor languages have objects, abstraction, concurrency, but neither classes nor inheritance [31]. Messaging is included in this definition as a means to implement a concurrency model. We omit further discussion of actor languages (for a more detailed discussion, see [2, 31]). However, we conclude that the importance of the messaging metaphor is disputed in literature.

In sum, to Kay, messages play an essential role in the object-oriented paradigm [16]. However, to Wegner, messaging plays a subordinate role, and thus the role of messaging for object-oriented programming is subject to debate [31].

Polymorphism Thomas highlights an important implication of messaging [30]. Objects can be substituted for each other, as long as they guarantee that they respond to the same set of messages. Objects can implement their own specific implementation of an operation, but can be treated equivalently, as long as they can receive the same messages. Thomas uses the term *polymorphism* (from Greek “many forms”) to describe this concept:

The ability of different objects to respond differently to the same message is known as polymorphism. [30][pp. 232]

This mechanism allows programmers to replace objects with other objects, or treat them as collections. This can help to replace complex case-switching facilities with dynamic message dispatch. For example, a procedure that draws shapes, needs to know whether to draw a circle or a rectangle. This information can be passed to the procedure using some kind of integer flag (e.g., 1 for rectangles, 2 for circles). With a polymorphic object, however, it is possible to send the same `draw` message. Depending on whether the object is a `rectangle` or a `circle`, the program will draw one or the other, which is the core idea of dynamic message dispatch.

Stefik and Bobrow uphold a similar definition of polymorphism [28]:

In general the term polymorphism means ‘having or assuming different forms’, but in the context of object-oriented programming, it refers to the capability for different classes of objects to respond to exactly the same protocols. [28]

Stefik and Bobrow define a *protocol* as “a standardized set of messages for implementing something” [28], which renders their view of polymorphism congruent with the views of Thomas [30]: Polymorphism means that objects can respond to the same set of messages. Note also that they use the more general concept of a (semantic) protocol than that of a (syntactic) interface.

It is important to note that there is much more to polymorphism than we covered here, as, for example, Pierce elaborates [20]. Pierce mentions different kinds of polymorphism, such as parametric (e.g., generics), ad-hoc (e.g., method overloading), and subtype polymorphism (e.g., inheritance), only to name a few. We omit further details of this idea for brevity. Pierce comments on this topic as follows:

The unqualified term “polymorphism” causes a certain amount of confusion between programming languages communities. Among functional programmers (i.e., those who use or design languages like ML, Haskell, etc.), it almost always refers to parametric polymorphism. Among object-oriented programmers, on the other hand, it almost always means subtype polymorphism, while the term genericity (or generics) is used for parametric polymorphism. [20][pp. 341]

In a nutshell, the term polymorphism refers to a complex subject, is used in different contexts outside of object-oriented programming, and is a homonym in different areas, which altogether leads to confusion, as Pierce mentions.

The definitions of object-oriented aspects discussed in this section focus on the *mechanisms* that constitute the object-oriented paradigm. In other words, they describe *how* to do object-oriented programming. However, members of the software engineering community have partly different views on the respective mechanisms concerning their significance for OOP. While to some, OOP requires classes [5, 31], others say that messaging is the key feature of object-oriented programming and ignore classes [16]. The number of mechanisms and the imprecise use and reuse of terms adds to the complexity of the subject and contributes to the confusion.

3.2 The Hermeneutic View: Why Is Object Orientation Used?

As for why object-oriented programming is applied, we found several reasons in our corpus of articles. They can be summarized as: reuse, modularity, problem decomposition, and program comprehension.

Reuse In programming languages, functions can be defined to group together programming language primitives (statements and expressions). This enables programmers to cause the same effect multiple times, possibly with different parameters. For example, a windowing system must be able to draw a window. When the window is moved, the application must draw the same window, but at a different location. To accomplish this, drawing primitives (e.g., drawing a line, filling an area) can be grouped into routines, procedures, or functions (e.g., drawing a frame, drawing a background), and finally, multiple operations of this sort can be grouped to become objects (e.g., a menu, an error message).

By grouping primitives together, programmers can reapply them: They *reuse* the code in a different context. Abadi and Cardelli outline [1]:

A software component is reusable when it can be easily used in more than one context. [...] In all cases, reuse entails the replacement of a component (or a placeholder) with another component in a context. [1]

In sum, components that are capable of taking place in a context other than the first context that they were designed for are said to be *reusable*.

The purpose of reusing software or its parts is to reduce the amount of work that needs to be done. If a component fulfills a purpose and can be reused in a similar or different context, then programmers can avoid the extra work of writing another such component.

Several object-oriented mechanisms from the formalistic view facilitate reuse:

1. **Polymorphism:** Objects can replace other objects as a whole, as long as their interface stays the same.
2. **Inheritance:** Subclasses can re-implement only specific methods (i.e., *override* them), while retaining existing methods (i.e., inherit them). Inheritance allows classes to stand in for other classes within a hierarchy.
3. **Composition:** Objects can interact with other objects and recombine them to form modular units.
4. **Encapsulation:** Encapsulation hides internal details and allows internal data representations to be changed or replaced, as long as the objects' public boundaries stay intact.

While there is no agreement on the different mechanisms that constitute the object-oriented paradigm as a whole (classes, inheritance, messages, etc.), there is some agreement on the idea of *reuse* and objects as a means to reuse code, either in part (refining an object through inheritance) or as a whole (replacing an object).

Snyder substantiates this idea [27]: When a subclass inherits from a superclass, it may keep some methods and replace others. As a result, objects of this class share (and thus reuse) some parts of the classes' implementation. To Snyder, the idea that "*objects can share partial implementation*" is an essential property of the object-oriented paradigm, and as a result, the whole paradigm facilitates reuse:

Sharing part of an implementation results in the same type of maintenance and size benefits that sharing a full implementation provides [...]. It also makes reuse possible when requirements are similar but not identical. [27][pp. 38]

Also Thomas advocates the reuse of code [30]:

Reusing, rather than reinventing, software speeds the development and maintenance of large applications. [30][pp. 231]

Thomas outlines that inheritance is the essential feature facilitating reuse:

Inheritance increases code sharing by allowing the language rather than the programmer to reuse code from one class in another related class. [30][pp. 234]

So far, we found agreement on the reuse of code, but there is no universal agreement on how to achieve reuse best. We outlined the tense relationship between encapsulation and inheritance in Section 3.1 (as outlined by Snyder [26]), and Wegner concurs [32]: The sharing mechanisms that other authors praise (i.e., inheritance) can cause problems in different situations. Objects tie operations and data together, and thus operations could access variables that are used by different objects as well. This may cause conflicts, as Wegner attests:

Object oriented programming sacrifices the reusability of individual operations to gain efficiency and conceptual simplicity. [32][pp. 247]

Wegner describes that object-oriented programming shifts the scope of reuse away from operations to objects (as [1,5,26,30] also describe). In object-oriented programming, individual operations become less applicable in different contexts (i.e., they are less reusable), but this only supports the idea that objects should be the conceptual unit of reuse.

Reuse is related to modularity. To reuse a component, it must be reapplied in another context. For this process to succeed, the element of reuse must not depend on external elements – it must be modular, a self-contained element, with clear boundaries. We discuss this aspect of *modularity* next.

Modularity Abstractly, modularity describes the degree to which the parts of a system can be combined and separated. Modularity is a system’s property of being modular.

In this regard, objects (and their classes) themselves are modules, and they contribute to systems’ modularity. Objects define clear boundaries and interfaces; they are self-contained in that their data and operations on these data are positioned closely together. But objects can form modules in another way: They can be grouped together to form larger, intermediate, reusable units. In some programming language eco-systems, the physical containers of reuse are even called *modules*. For example, in Python, a code file can contain multiple classes or runnable objects and is considered a module. Ada or Object Pascal support modules explicitly with language constructs. On a larger scale, modules can themselves be regrouped and thus form libraries and frameworks, or programs and applications. According to Booch and colleagues, forming modules creates *modularity* [5]:

Modularity is the property of a system that has been decomposed into a set of cohesive and loosely coupled modules. [5][pp. 528]

Modules must be *cohesive*. Their parts are not grouped randomly, but should be logically related to each other. Modules should also be *loosely coupled*, that is,

they should be as independent as possible from other modules, in that changes in one module do not cause changes in another, but be able to interact with them. In sum, programmers must define modules' *boundaries*.

Modules are treated as large units of reuse that group cohesive entities together, but these properties apply to objects as well. Objects group data and operations together, or can combine other objects to form more complex objects (see *composite objects*). Objects are not the same as modules, but they are *modular* in nature, in that they can be combined and arranged in novel ways, independent of their original scope or purpose, and thus are units of reuse.

Several authors support this argument: Wegner points out that in the Modula programming languages, objects are called modules, and calls them “modular computing agents” [31][p. 172]. Booch and colleagues underscore that objects are appropriate means of creating modular systems [5], and Thomas mentions that Simula uses objects as the “natural unit of modularity” [30][pp. 231], and Aldrich declares “modular extensibility” as a unique benefit of objects [3].

While there is agreement that modularity is desirable for the economic development of software, the means to accomplish modularity are somewhat unclear. Programmers get to decide where to draw boundaries, but there are different ways to do so. Parnas outlines criteria on how to best draw modules' boundaries [18]: A module should reveal as little as possible about its inner workings, so that modules correspond to *design decisions* that programmers have to make – a principle he calls *information hiding*.

In contrast, a system can be modularized by creating a module for each step of data processing, such that the resulting structure resembles a flowchart. Parnas points out deficiencies of this approach in that it produces a module structure in which it is difficult to manipulate modules individually and changes affect many places at once. Parnas argues that modularization along design decisions results in a system that is easier to change, can be developed independently, and is easier to comprehend.

To recapitulate, modularity is the degree to which components of a system can be composed. Modularity facilitates *reuse*. Objects are modular in nature, and thus are meant to facilitate the reuse of code. In the following, we use the term object and module interchangeably.

There are different ways to create modules, and Parnas suggests that a system can be encoded as a flowchart-like sequence of steps, or a set of design decisions, that hide information. The process of deciding which modules to use to represent aspects of a problem is called *problem decomposition*.

Problem Decomposition Programs are not isolated entities, but they perform operations or calculations that represent some thing or process from the real world. For example, a calculator supports a user in adding numbers, a spreadsheet supports accounting, and a shopping cart helps users to purchase goods from a Web site. These real-world problems are usually transferred to a programmer as some kind of *problem statement* [24]. From this statement, programmers build an understanding (i.e., a *mental representation*) that allows

them to mentally manipulate the problem of finding a solution and drawing inferences about the situation. We use the general idea of a *problem statement* here, and ignore the details of how such statements are delivered. This can be accomplished using a verbal conversation, or more formally, a user story, or some kind of requirements specification.

To solve a problem, programmers must first build a mental representation of the problem (i.e., they must understand the problem), and then teach a computer their mental model, by encoding their understanding using a programming language into a form that the machine can translate and execute. Identifying the involved parts of the problem statement is called *decomposition* of the *problem*, which results in decisions on what aspects of a real-world system to represent, and how to represent them, that is, which units of modularization to use.

In the scope of larger programs, the relevant entities are not mere memory fields and variables, but rather larger units, such as processes or goals. As Parnas outlines, choosing data-processing steps as representations for problems has its limitations and yields programs that are more difficult to maintain [18]. Thus, the result of a decomposition should be larger units, such as objects or modules, that hide design decisions.

Problem decomposition is not the same as creating modules: We contrast problem decomposition and modularization as follows:

1. **Modularization** is the process of creating modules while focusing on a system's resulting modularity.
2. **Problem Decomposition** is the process of deciding what aspects of a problem statement to concentrate on and how to represent an understanding of a problem with programmatic units (i.e., modules).

Problem decomposition is the preliminary step for *modularization*, which is applied to the problem itself, that is, situations, issues, and processes from the real world are analyzed and broken up into manageable, cohesive pieces. In contrast, *modularization* applies to a software system and its code, which results in modular units (e.g., objects, modules). In short, decomposition focuses on manageable units from the problem domain, whereas modularization focuses on the resulting code structures. This difference can be understood as an instance of the contrasting formalistic and hermeneutic perspectives. Modularization is a formalist perspective, concerned with the static properties of classes and objects, whereas problem decomposition is concerned with an interpretation of the real world – a rather epistemological perspective.

Parnas shows that in the software development process, the step of decomposing a system into modules can be done in different ways: One with focus on the problem, and another with focus on the solution. Ideally, both strategies yield equivalent results in that the modules correspond to the pieces of the problem statement, but as Parnas outlines, it is possible to decompose a problem into incongruent module structures.

We established earlier that objects are modular in nature. Hence, we conclude that the different strategies to decompose systems into modules applies

to decomposition into objects in the same way: Decomposition of a problem can yield an object structure that is difficult to maintain, a stance that other authors mention. Analogous to Parnas [18], Booch and others describe *algorithmic decomposition* and *object-oriented decomposition* as orthogonal methods of decomposition [5]. They define them as:

Algorithmic Decomposition: The process of breaking a system into parts, each of which represents some small step in a larger process. The application of structured design methods leads to an algorithmic decomposition, whose focus is on the flow of control within a system.

Object-Oriented Decomposition: The process of breaking a system into parts, each of which represents some class or object from the problem domain. The application of object-oriented design methods leads to an object-oriented decomposition, in which we view the world as a collection of objects that cooperate with one another to achieve some desired functionality. [5][pp. 522; 529]

The first perspective is equivalent to Parnas' idea of a flowchart-like decomposition. The latter emphasizes that objects are appropriate representations to decompose systems into modular structures. Booch and others call the process of analyzing and thus decomposing problem statements from the real world into objects "object-oriented analysis" [5].

Composition and decomposition form a reciprocal pair. Decomposition results in an understanding which is encoded into units. Composition arranges these units in relation with each other. If decomposition is done correctly, it results in reusable pieces that can be repurposed and reused within compositions. West illustrates this idea with the following metaphor:

Any child with a screwdriver and a hammer can take things apart. Unless another child can look at the pieces and determine how to put them together again [...], the first child's decomposition was flawed. [34][p. 78]

The quality of software depends on the programmers' decisions on the boundaries of the software's constituting parts. If the software is appropriately decomposed, the resulting elements can be reused or even re-purposed appropriately. In a nutshell, proper decomposition defines the scope of changeability, use, and reuse.

To summarize, managing the complex nature of problems to be solved when creating software, it is crucial to *decompose* the problem appropriately and to create *modules*. Objects facilitate reuse, are self-contained, encapsulate data and thus have clear boundaries. They can be reapplied in different context. In sum, objects are appropriate units of modularization. But are they appropriate units of decomposition? Do they *hide information* and represent *design decisions*, rather than *algorithmic steps*? To answer this question, we need to look at the process of problem decomposition from a psychological perspective. That is, we include the internal, mental states, and processes of programmers into the discussion, which are researched in the field of *Program Comprehension*.

Program Comprehension As Booch and colleagues outline [5], object-oriented decomposition yields structures in which the operands and operations of a problem statement are represented as objects. That is, objects correspond to entities (i.e., being things) from the real world, and *represent* them in a computer system. When choosing representations, programmers decide *how* to represent entities from the real world as objects. They get to decide which aspects to ignore and which aspects to include into the new representation. Because the *representation* can never be complete, in other words, the map is not the territory, it is also an *abstraction*. Unfortunately, we found that the two terms are used interchangeably in the literature, and thus we define and discuss these concepts in separation.

In short, to *represent* means to define an entity that stands in for another, and to *abstract* means to filter out details of an entity for a specific purpose. We subsume these aspects under the label *comprehension* because these processes are relevant for programming in general. When software is initially created, a problem statement is “encoded”. When a bug is being fixed or a feature is to be added, the code is “decoded” to return an understanding of the software, and the problem it solves. In a nutshell, program comprehension is necessary for software creation and maintenance. Abstraction and representation are general concepts that are relevant in this regard.

Abstraction

Programmers must decide where to draw module boundaries, so that modules hide internal details, but still are able to collaborate (i.e., provide functionality to be reused by other modules). Module boundaries shield modules’ *internal details* from their *surrounding environment*. In other words, a module’s boundaries separate its *inside* from its *outside*.

Explicit boundaries allow programmers to ignore a module’s internal details, and treat it as an *abstraction* instead. Generally, to abstract means to filter information of a thing or phenomenon to form categories⁶. Describing the nature of this process is difficult, because its meaning varies between software engineering, mathematics, and linguistics. However, there is consensus that *abstract* things are contrasted with *concrete* things, although it is unclear how a distinction between these two poles should be drawn⁷.

Abstraction has long been recognized as an important concept by other authors. Dahl, Dijkstra, and Hoare outline how abstraction helps to reduce complexity:

Abstraction arises from a recognition of similarities between certain objects, situations, or processes in the real world, and the decision to concentrate on these similarities, and to ignore for the time being the differences. [11]

⁶ <https://www.britannica.com/science/abstraction/>

⁷ <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/abstract-objects/>

Booch and others state [5]:

An abstraction denotes the essential characteristics of an object that distinguish it from all other kinds of objects and thus provide crisply defined conceptual boundaries, relative to the perspective of the viewer. [5][p. 44]

In summary, boundaries and abstraction go hand in hand.

Abstraction can be considered in layers, in that *lower layers* can be abstracted with *higher layers*. Snyder illustrates this idea with an example [27]:

A file is an abstraction of persistent storage, at a higher level than the actual storage devices. [...] Abstractions appear at every level of a system. Higher level abstractions are implemented in terms of lower level abstractions. [27][pp. 32]

Persistent storage requires magnetic state changes on a metal disk or chip, but programmers usually interface this process by saving to a file, which is an abstraction provided by the operating system's file system. At the lowest level, the file system communicates with a device driver. Thus, magnetic states are abstracted over many layers and these layers are said to be on a higher level (e.g., file) or on a lower level (e.g., magnetic states).

Abstraction has several meanings in the object-oriented paradigm. For example, in Java or C#, the keyword `abstract` indicates a class that cannot be instantiated as an object (whereas some subclasses of it can). We consider this an implementation detail of these languages and focus on the idea that objects can be arranged to filter aspects and details of other objects.

Not only do objects abstract details of data, but they are capable of creating new layers of abstractions. Such layers can be formed based on classes using *inheritance*, or objects, using *composition*. With inheritance, super-classes are considered more abstract, and inheriting subclasses are considered more concrete. Composition allows objects to encapsulate other objects as their state, thus abstracting from their details. In sum, objects abstract, and can themselves be used to create new abstractions.

We introduced *abstraction* earlier when we discussed *data abstraction* (cf. Section 3.1). However, objects are not merely data abstractions, but their capability to be regrouped and composed allows programmers to define another kind of abstraction that the term *data abstraction* fails to express: A composite object can publish methods to calculate or manipulate some data, but it may shift the responsibilities to resolve details of the process to other collaborating objects, or delegate them to a different implementation. Cook calls this idea *procedural abstraction* [6]. Aldrich extends this idea and coins the term *service abstraction* to underscore that operations do not need to manipulate data, but can have other kinds of effects [3]. For example, they can invoke complex calculations by using other objects. Aldrich cites Kay, who stated that:

[...] objects should be presented as sites of higher level behaviors more appropriate for use as dynamic components. [14]

This places the object’s behavior, that is, the collective effect of their operations, into focus. Building on this idea, Aldrich outlines:

The key design leverage provided by objects is the ability to define non-trivial abstractions that are modularly extensible, where instances of those extensions can interoperate in a first-class way. [3][pp. 2]

Aldrich further explains: *Nontrivial abstraction* is the capability of objects to provide complex services. This requires more than one operation because a single operation can be abstracted by a singular function; however, this is only true if state memory is not part of this definition. *Modular extensibility* is a system’s ability to accept new implementations without changing the original implementation. *Interoperability* refers to the invocation of methods on instances with different implementations but a uniform interface.

Representation In the above definitions, the terms abstraction and representation are mingled together. Aldrich speaks of abstractions, but the core idea is representation. We have defined earlier that to abstract means to filter details about an entity. This is an intellectual process, as programmers get to decide what to exclude and what to include. The structures that result from encoding entities from the real world into code are called *representations*. For example, a person can be represented as an integer – in a program that is meant to count the views of a website, this representation is abstract, but sufficient nonetheless. For a program that manages individuals at an insurance company, however, a simple integer would be too abstract (i.e., filtering too many details), and more details would have to be included, such as name and socio-demographic data.

While the level of abstraction varies, both an integer and the complex structure correspond to entities from the real world (people), and thus *represent* them.

In sum, Aldrich outlines that the benefit of objects lies in their capability to represent sets of operations, and that these operations together form new units of reasoning. For example, an object for a display system represents what behavior is relevant to a user, instead of abstracting manipulations of a data structure. A service abstraction describes a broader concept and captures the idea of state data to be manipulated. This interpretation is congruent with Kay, in that objects are capable of representing higher level *goals*.

Snyder substantiates this idea even further [27][p. 32]. He discusses the object-oriented landscape extensively and identifies eleven core concepts of object-oriented programming:

- All objects embody an abstraction.
- Objects provide services.
- Clients issue requests.
- Objects are encapsulated.
- Requests identify operations.
- Requests can identify objects.

- New objects can be created.
- Operations can be generic.
- Objects can be classified in terms of their services.
- Objects can have a common implementation.
- Objects can share partial implementations.

As his first point, Snyder names an object’s ability to abstract, and discusses the benefit therein explicitly: “Clients manipulate meaningful entities. They are not responsible for interpreting data”. This view is congruent with the views of Cook and Aldrich that objects abstract data, but the benefit they offer is better characterized with their capability to provide *meaningful abstractions*, in that they provide *services* or complex behavior and define how data and subordinate behaviors should be interpreted. This again is an example of a convoluted understanding of abstraction and representation because providing a meaningful abstraction is the same as representing another idea or concept. The core idea is not that objects can hide the details of entities, but provide meaningful abstractions, in that they stand in for a concept. In other words, objects are *representations*.

To summarize, *objects* are *modular units of reuse* that form *abstractions*. Their capability to abstract allows them to stand in for arbitrary concepts, such as *goals*, *services*, or anything that has an effect (i.e., as *behavior*). As Snyder outlines, the abstractions that objects embody provide *meaning*, in that they suggest how data is to be interpreted. Hence, objects are *representations* of entities from the real world. This relationship is important: It has long been argued that objects appear to be appropriate units of decomposition, because the real world also consists of *objects*, and thus objects must be *natural* representations of things from the real world. We investigate this idea next.

Physical and Virtual Representations So far, we discussed that objects are representations, that is, their encodings (in the form of classes and their instances) correspond to things from the real world. But what things can be represented? Above, we used the term entity, to mean “a thing that is”, and this term is not limited to physical being things, but also to virtual, mental, or spiritual things, such as categories, processes, and concepts. Aldrich mentions this by referring to objects as *service abstractions* [3]. That is, objects are capable of representing services, and a service is arguably less concrete and physical than, e.g., a lion or a car.

Objects can represent physical things symbolically, but are also capable of representing more abstract entities. We outlined this idea earlier, when we discussed the view that objects can be viewed as *behavioral abstractions* or *service abstractions*. Based on our work so far, we reinterpret these terms: Objects are *behavioral representations*, or *service representations*, and encoding these representations requires abstracting from their details. In this scope, Aldrich mentions that service abstractions support *goals* [3]:

[...] *The power of objects is not in representing data structures, but in representing higher-level goals.* [3][pp. 4]

Goals are arguably abstract. For example, the goal to *advance my career* does not dictate any specific steps and is interpreted differently by different people. In a nutshell, objects are capable of representing arbitrary things, and are not limited to representing physical entities. Booch and others observed this as well [5]:

From the perspective of human cognition, an object is any of the following:

- *A tangible and/or visible thing*
- *Something that may be comprehended intellectually*
- *Something toward which thought or action is directed*

Booch and colleagues collected several sources of objects, that is, things from the real world that can be analyzed and represented by objects, such as roles, events, interactions, places, things, people, locations, and organizations. In other words, objects are abstract symbols that are capable of representing physical or virtual being things from the real world, such as concepts, events, or processes.

Naturalness & the Human Factor In their historic origin, the idea of naturalness was a driving force behind the adoption of objects: When Dahl and others conceived objects in Simula, they viewed them as realizations of “natural, easily conceived components” that allowed programmers to easily manage complexity. They state explicitly that objects were meant as a means of handling the complexity of large simulation programs, by “decompos[ing] [a] problem into natural, easily conceived components”. Their ideas were supposed to “make [...] communication between programmers easier”, as well as enabling “non-specialist[s] [...] to solve small and medium-sized problems without specialist help” [8]. But whether this relationship is *natural* depends on the programmer.

The notion of *naturalness* can be found in the work of other authors: Rentsch states that viewing objects from the outside (i.e., as abstractions) is a *natural* perspective [22]:

The first principle of object oriented programming might be called intelligence encapsulation: view objects from outside to provide a natural metaphor of intrinsic behavior.

[...] in explaining object oriented programming objects are viewed from outside. [...] the view from outside is the natural one [...]. [22][pp. 52]

Other notions of naturalness are less explicit. Abadi and Cardelli call the capability of objects to *represent* elements of physical systems *intuitive*. Here, the idea of intuition means that representative relationships with the real world are directly perceivable features of objects, or at least that realizing the correspondence between a system and its simulation requires no prior conscious thought:

The object oriented approach to programming is based on an intuitive correspondence between a software simulation of a physical system and the physical system itself. [1]

Objects have no a-priori connection to the things they represent from real world. In other words, objects are *symbolic*. Their connection to real-world entities is provided by programmers, and thus whether they represent something *naturally* depends on how programmers perceive their surrounding environment. Additionally, it depends on their knowledge or on other individual experiences, and capability to encode their perceptions, experiences and knowledge into a program.

We note that Simula's name reflects the frame in which it was conceived, that is, to represent the elements of simulations. The programmers choose appropriate abstractions to simulate real-world processes or systems over time. Therefore, objects were conceived to represent things from the real world, but whether this fit is *natural* or *intuitive* cannot be generally answered.

Conception From a technical perspective, modularity is a meaningful indicator to decide whether parts of the system can be reused. But modularity is also connected to the human factor, in that objects correspond to concepts, and they help programmers to deal with the complexity of the system. While objects were conceived as a means to restructure code, they were also conceived as a means of comprehension:

In order to decompose the problem into natural, easily conceived components, each part should be describable as an individual program.

By decomposing a large problem, one can obtain component problems of manageable size to be dealt with one at a time, and each containing a limited number of details.

Suitable decomposition is an absolute requirement if more than one person takes part in the analysis and programming. [8][pp. 1, 4]

The authors describe that, to solve a problem, the problem must be decomposed into *manageable* and *conceivable units* that allow programmers to *communicate* their understanding of the problem with other programmers.

Objects may help to facilitate communication between programmers. Programmers can abstract details of data manipulation or other operations using objects, which relieves their colleagues of the responsibility to interpret the data. Snyder says:

An object explicitly embodies an abstraction that is meaningful to its clients.

Clients manipulate meaningful entities. They are not responsible for interpreting data. [26][pp. 32]

Dahl and colleagues outline that properly decomposed systems yield modules that can be understood one unit at a time. We stated that modules form abstractions (that is, they allow programmers to filter their details), and Liskov supports this argument [17]:

Abstraction when supported by specifications and encapsulation provides locality within a program. Locality allows a program to be implemented, understood, or modified one module at a time. [17][pp. 20]

Here, Liskov adds that locality supports *understanding* software one module at a time. The boundaries that objects define through encapsulation provide such locality. Liskov calls objects' outside interface their *specifications*.

The implementer of a using module knows what to expect from an abstraction, namely the behavior described by the specification. [17][pp. 20]

This reflects Snyders' interpretation that objects, being abstractions, provide *meaning*, and thus programmers can form expectations about their behavior.

Abstraction and modularity imply that software can be understood one module at a time, which allows programmers to manipulate these units in isolation from other units. In other words, objects can be changed without affecting other objects. Changing only one thing instead of many things at once is an important step towards reducing complexity. Parnas' information hiding, embodied by encapsulation, is an appropriate principle to achieve this feature [18]: Information Hiding is the heuristic a programmer uses to identify cohesive units of responsibilities.

Rentsch portrays similar implications of decomposing a problem and thus achieving modularity [22]. He uses the synonym *factoring* to express the idea of decomposing a system into units:

[...] factoring, the property of one thing being in only one place. Successful factoring produces brevity, clarity, modularity, concinnity, and synchronicity, which in turn provide manageability in complex systems. [22][pp. 54; Author's emphasis]

According to Rentsch, *factoring* (or modularization) produces *clarity*, and thus renders complex systems more *manageable*, both of which are aspects that are relevant to humans. Programmers need to be able to manage the complexity, and clarity is helpful in this regard. Thomas [30][pp. 231] claims that object-oriented systems can be "readily comprehended". For example, a financial application, dealing with object representations of customers, debit, credit, and accounts can be understood by users familiar with this particular domain.

In a nutshell, *objects* provide meaning. They are conceived to support *comprehension* of programs. Their modular characteristics draw boundaries and thus form abstractions, which allow programmers to ignore internal details and focus on their purpose. The intention is to reduce the complexity of the software. Most authors accept that objects were conceived as a means to handling complexity.

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